

Non-Technological Innovation: A Catalyst for Sustainable Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

As MSMEs face increasing pressure to remain competitive in a dynamic economic environment, non-technological innovation has emerged as a critical driver of sustainability. This study investigates the influence of non-technological innovation on the sustainable growth of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria, with a specific focus on organisational and marketing innovations. The research employed a quantitative approach, gathering data from 418 respondents through structured questionnaires distributed to selected MSMEs across key Nigerian states. Data analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0. The findings highlight that organisational innovation has a positive but weak influence on sustainable MSME growth, suggesting that changes in internal structures, work routines, and managerial practices are supportive but not strongly impactful. On the other hand, marketing innovation exhibited a stronger and highly significant effect on sustainable growth, underscoring the importance of innovative marketing strategies, customer relationship management, and market positioning. These results highlight marketing innovation as a more potent catalyst for sustainable MSME growth in the Nigerian context. The study recommends targeted policies and capacity-building programmes that support non-technological innovation, particularly in marketing.

Keywords: Marketing Innovation, Non-Technological Innovation, Nigerian MSMEs, Organisational Innovation, Sustainable Growth.

1.0 Introduction

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a pivotal role in Nigeria's economy, accounting for over 90% of businesses and contributing around 50% to employment and GDP (SMEDAN, 2021; PwC, 2024). However, these enterprises face numerous challenges such as poor infrastructure, limited access to finance, and weak management. To remain sustainable and competitive, MSMEs require innovative strategies beyond conventional technological solutions. Non-technological innovation particularly organisational and marketing innovation—has emerged as a transformative approach (Sinha *et al.*, 2024). Organisational innovation involves implementing new methods in business operations, structures, and relationships to enhance adaptability and performance. For Nigerian MSMEs plagued by informal systems, this can involve restructuring processes, adopting quality frameworks, or forging strategic alliances. Studies show that organisational innovation improves coherence, employee motivation, and long-term resilience, which are vital in Nigeria's volatile business environment (Sciarelli *et al.*, 2020; Alabi *et al.*, 2022).

Marketing innovation, on the other hand, enables MSMEs to revamp their marketing mix to meet changing consumer demands. Through strategies such as digital marketing and e-commerce, firms enhance market reach, customer loyalty, and brand strength (Achmad, 2023; Chukwuma & Adebayo, 2021). This is particularly relevant in Nigeria's increasingly competitive and digitalised market space. Despite these benefits, adoption of non-technological innovation among Nigerian MSMEs remains low due to poor capacity, weak institutional support, and policy neglect. Most innovation policies prioritize technological infrastructure, overlooking simpler, scalable non-technological innovations that can deliver significant results for MSMEs (Akinbinu & Edun, 2020; Nwosu & Okolo, 2023).

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria operate in an increasingly competitive and dynamic economic environment where sustaining long-term growth remains a major challenge. While technological innovation has received significant attention as a growth driver, the role of non-technological innovation particularly organisational and marketing innovation remains insufficiently explored in the Nigerian MSME context. This gap limits the understanding of how internal management practices and innovative marketing strategies contribute to sustainable enterprise development. By identifying the relative impact of these innovations, the study provides valuable insights for policymakers, business owners, and development agencies seeking practical strategies to strengthen MSME competitiveness and sustainability. Therefore, this study examines the influence of organisational and marketing innovation on the sustainable growth of MSMEs in Nigeria using quantitative data from selected states.

2.0 Literature, theoretical model and research hypothesis

2.1 Nature of non-technological innovation.

Non-technological innovation involves improvements in organisational structures, business models, management practices, and marketing strategies that enhance firm performance without relying on new technologies (Kanojia & Singh, 2023). Unlike technological innovation, which focuses on product and process advancements, non-technological innovation emphasises operational and strategic changes such as leadership, culture, and collaboration that foster adaptability, especially in developing economies with limited access to advanced technology (Siriram, 2022; Amoah *et al.*, 2023). This form of innovation also plays a foundational role in supporting technological innovation. Organisational and marketing innovations enhance the effectiveness of technological solutions, particularly where supportive institutional environments exist (Vu *et al.*, 2022; Vo-Thai *et al.*, 2021). Non-technological capabilities like management and transactional competence also contribute significantly to financial and innovation outcomes, often yielding higher long-term benefits than technology alone (Nascimento *et al.*, 2024).

These insights reveal that human-centered and process-driven innovation approaches are essential. Investments in internal resources such as human capital, strategic routines, and organisational structure can better position firms for sustainable growth, especially in manufacturing and service sectors with limited R&D focus. Despite its importance, non-technological innovation remains underemphasized in policy and research. As highlighted by Tsambou and Djoumessi (2025), inclusive innovation strategies must integrate management and marketing innovations to reflect diverse socio-economic realities, especially in emerging economies.

2.2 Organisational innovation and sustainable MSMEs growth

Organizational innovation (OI) refers to the use of innovative approaches in business practices, workplace structures, and external relationships that are critical for attaining long-term success among MSMEs (Baumane-Vītoliņa *et al.*, 2022; Ajayi & Tolulope, 2023). It involves revising management strategies, procedures, and collaboration mechanisms to enhance adaptability and efficiency (Onyekuru & Ugwu, 2021; Ndace *et al.*, 2024). OI transforms internal systems to optimise resource use and performance, fostering a culture that supports continuous innovation (Khurana *et al.*, 2021; AlAnazi *et al.*, 2022; Susantinah & Krishernawan, 2023). OI is actualised through innovation in business practices (IBP), workplace organisation (IWO), and external relations (IER). IBP includes tools like Lean production and quality management systems to enhance efficiency (Dukeov *et al.*, 2020), while IWO empowers employees through decentralisation and flexibility. IER strengthens collaboration with stakeholders to facilitate innovation and competitiveness (OECD-Eurostat, 2005; Dora and Saudi, 2020).

The Resource-Based View (RBV) hypothesis suggests that enterprises may gain a competitive edge by utilizing valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources. MSMEs can use internal assets such as leadership, local expertise, and an innovative culture to promote growth despite limited resources (Kalathingal and Ambrammal, 2025). Empirical studies confirm that OI, when aligned with strategic internal resources, improves MSMEs' resilience and sustainability in changing environments. Integrating innovation with financial and capital strategies promotes long-term viability and contributes to inclusive economic development (Rijal and Supriandi, 2024). Hence, we propose the first hypothesis:

Ho₁: *Organisational innovation has no significant effect on the sustainable MSMEs growth in Nigeria.*

2.2 Marketing innovation and sustainable MSMEs growth

Marketing innovation (MI) is a crucial driver of sustainable growth for MSMEs, especially in today's competitive and digital economy. It involves implementing significantly new marketing strategies in areas like product design, pricing, promotion, and placement (Athaide *et al.*, 2025). MI enables MSMEs to differentiate their offerings, penetrate new markets, and maintain competitiveness. Based on the Resource-Based View (RBV), marketing competencies are viewed as strategic resources that must be valuable, unique, inimitable, and non-substitutable in order to produce long-term benefits. Digital marketing innovation is extremely transformational. Social media engagement, SEO, and content marketing are among the strategies used by MSMEs to improve consumer interaction, manage data, and cut marketing expenditures (Ohara *et al.*, 2024). Combined with green branding and sustainability messaging, digital tools may benefit both economic, environmental and social goals (Marhandrie, 2023)

Beyond digital platforms, MI becomes more impactful when integrated with organisational capabilities like branding and market orientation. A holistic approach strengthens customer loyalty and operational performance, emphasizing RBV's stance on internal resource investment and learning (Budiman and Ardhiyansyah, 2023; Wijayanto *et al.*, 2024). However, MI must be aligned with a broader strategic framework, supported by culture, long-term planning, and ecosystem enablers such as training, funding, and digital infrastructure to deliver sustainable growth (Nmadu & Silas 2018; Pasaribu *et al.*, 2025). Considering the preceding claims, we suggest the following hypothesis:

Ho₂: *Marketing innovation has no significant effect on the sustainable MSMEs growth in Nigeria.*

2.3 Sustainable MSMEs growth

Sustainable growth of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is critical

for balanced economic development, job creation, and poverty reduction, particularly in developing countries (Prakash *et al.*, 2023). MSMEs act as engines of inclusive growth by promoting industrialization in rural and semi-urban regions, thereby reducing income disparities and regional imbalances (Singla, 2023). Their contribution to GDP, exports, and employment signifies their strategic role in achieving national and global sustainable development goals (Shailendra, 2024). However, the growth trajectory of MSMEs is often hindered by financial constraints, technological lag, and inadequate policy implementation (Kumari, 2025). Access to finance and strategic financial management are major determinants of MSMEs' sustainability (Olubiyi, 2022; Dewi *et al.*, 2025). Evidence from Nigeria shows that firms lacking in financial planning, budgeting, and control are more likely to collapse (Dada *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, policies supporting affordable credit access and alternative financing like crowdfunding have proven effective in boosting growth and resilience (Mohammed *et al.*, 2025). Moreover, government support via tax education and streamlined tax processes plays a critical role in shaping a conducive environment for sustainable MSME development (Appah and Duoduo, 2023).

In the digital age, technology integration and sustainable digital marketing strategies are key to long-term MSME growth. Studies suggest that effective use of SEO, social media, and content marketing enhances market reach and competitiveness (Sinha, *et al.*, 2024; Hidayat *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, education, capital access, and technological advancement positively influence MSMEs' ability to remain competitive and sustainable in changing market environments (Meitriana *et al.*, 2024). Thus, a holistic ecosystem involving financial literacy, supportive policies, and digital innovation is imperative for driving sustainable MSME growth globally.

3. METHODOLOGY

A survey design was used to achieve the study's desired outcomes. The population included 36,672 chosen MSMEs registered with the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN 2023). Using simplified Slovin's Formula modified by Tania *at al.* (2022), a sample size of three hundred and ninety-six (396) MSMEs was obtained based on 95% confidence level, a standard deviation of 0.5, and a confidence interval (margin of error) of $\pm 5\%$. However, to cater for non-response bias (30% of 396 = 118.8, 119 approximately: $396 + 119 = 515$), a 30% (119) addition is made as suggested by Wright (2015). The study adopt purposive random sampling technique which ensured representation sample of MSMEs from various sectors of the economy across 36 States (including FCT Abuja). Primary data collected through online questionnaires were analysed. Hypotheses were tested using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, as well as regression analysis. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 eased data analysis, resulting in strong results that were consistent with the study's objectives.

The model is represented by:

$$MSMEg_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OI_{it} + \beta_2 MI_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

MSMEg = MSME growth OI = organizational innovation

MI = marketing innovation β_0 = Intercept

ϵ_{it} = Regression Coefficients = the error term.

Regression statistics are used to analyze the data at the 5% level of significance using SPSS. If the estimated t-value is equal to or larger than the table (critical) t-value, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative.

4. Results and Discussion

The researcher distributed 519 questionnaires, but only 504 were correctly completed and returned. This reflects a 97.0% response rate. The participants comprised of 201 males and 303 females representing approximately 25% and 75% respectively; age category range from young, middle and old ages representing 17%, 73% and 10% respectively, who responded to the instruments. The correlation descriptive statistics for relationship between variables of non-technological innovation and sustainable MSMES growth in Nigeria are presented in table 1

Table 1: Correlation coefficient

		OI	MI	SG
OI	Pearson Correlation	1	.225	.046
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008	.004
	N		504	504
MI	Pearson Correlation		1	.063*
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
	N			504
SG	Pearson Correlation			1
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N			

Source: Researcher's SPSS Output, (2025)

Table 1 illustrates the correlation coefficients between the variables, all of which are less than 0.9 but larger than 0.1. This implies that the variables correlate sufficiently to be employed in the study, and there is no risk of damaging multicollinearity.

Table 2 **Regression Output I**

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	136.807	2	114.249	426.613	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.346	401	.027		
	Total	138.153	403			

Source: Researcher's SPSS Output, (2025)

Table 2 shows the ANOVA for the association between non-technological innovation and long-term MSMES growth. The F-statistics read 426.613. The p-value is less than 0.05, suggesting that the model's association is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level.

Table 3: **Regression Output II**

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.382	.365	.363	.10574	1.631

Source: Researcher's SPSS Output, (2025)

Figure 3 shows the regression model summary. The model's R value of 0.382 reveals a positive and robust link between the combined variables of non-technological innovation and sustainable MSMES growth. The R square value (0.365) indicates that the independent factors account for about 36.5% of the variation in sustainable MSME growth. The corrected R square value (0.363) indicates that even when exogenous variables are included, the independent variables will still account for about 66.3% of the variation in sustainable MSMES development.

Table 4: Regression Output 3

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients				
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.845	.204		9.055	.000
	OI	.037	.011	.020	.725	.017
	MI	0.225	.062	.021	26.664	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SG

Source: Researcher's SPSS Output, (2025)

From table 4, the coefficient of Organisational Innovation (OI) is 0.037 which is positive which implies that the more MSMEs can implement new methods in business practices, workplace structures, or external relations the more the business growth will be sustained. The importance of this, however, may be determined using the t statistics. The t-statistic of organisational innovation (OI) was 0.725, with a p-value of 0.017. The p-value is less than 0.05, suggesting that the model's association is significant at the 95% confidence level. This implies that the study lacks sufficient statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which states that organisational innovation has no significant effects on the sustainable growth of MSMEs in Nigeria; thus, the study accepts its alternate hypothesis, which states that organisational innovation has a significant effect on the sustainable growth of MSMEs in Nigeria. The findings are in agreement with the reports of Dora and Saudi (2020), who stated when organization is innovative it will improve its improved competitive advantage, increase revenue and market share which can lead to a sustainable business growth. Also, (Khurana *et al.*, 2019; Wulandari and Koe, 2022), reported that the more innovative an organization is the more it enhances efficiency and cost savings for a sustainable growth. Khurana *et al.*, (2021) was of the opinion that organization innovation is very useful in creating and sustaining growth.

The marketing innovation (MI) coefficient is positive ($\beta = 0.665$). This suggests that implementing a new marketing idea or plan that is notably different from the company's prior tactics, such as changes in product design, packaging, placement,

promotion, or price, would not only help MSMEs to develop quickly but also sustain that growth. However, the significance of this may be determined using t statistics. The t-statistic for Marketing Innovation (MI) was 26.664 with a p-value of 0.00. The p-value is less than 0.05, suggesting that the model's association is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. This implies that the study lacks sufficient statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which states that marketing innovation has no significant effects on the sustainable growth of MSMEs; thus, the study accepts its alternate hypothesis, which states that marketing innovation has a significant effect on the sustainable growth of MSMEs. The findings corroborate with the previous studies (Dora and Saudi, 2020), which stated that marketing innovation is one of the most prominent promotional contrivance essential for the products and services that can be uses to sustain growth.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study investigated the importance of non-technological innovation, as assessed by organisational innovation (OI) and marketing innovation (MI), as a driver of long-term MSME growth in Nigeria. The findings indicate that both OI and MI have a considerable favourable impact on MSMEs' development and sustainability. While the impact of OI is relatively modest, it remains statistically significant, suggesting that improved internal processes, workplace structures, and external relations contribute meaningfully to long-term growth. MI, however, shows a strong and highly significant influence, emphasizing the importance of adopting innovative marketing strategies in achieving and maintaining rapid MSMEs growth and sustainability in Nigeria.

MSMEs should prioritize the integration of innovative marketing strategies such as new product presentation, pricing models, and promotional approaches to drive sustainable growth. Simultaneously, they should adopt progressive business practices to strengthen internal capabilities and adaptability. Policymakers and support agencies are encouraged to design programs that foster innovation culture, providing training and incentives for non-technological innovation across MSMEs.

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